

**BARASERTIB ATTENUATES CISPLATIN-INDUCED
HEPATOTOXICITY IN MICE****Faisal Alqussair¹, Mahmoud Elshal^{1*}, Mirhan N. Makled¹, Nashwa M. Abu-Elsaad^{1*}**¹Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Mansoura University,
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35516, Egypt.**ABSTRACT**

Background/Objectives: Cisplatin (CIS) is a widely used chemotherapeutic agent; however, its clinical use is limited by associated hepatotoxicity. The current study aimed at exploring, for the first time, protective potential of barasertib, a selective Aurora kinase B inhibitor, against CIS-induced hepatotoxicity, along with possible underlying mechanisms. **Methods:** Male mice were treated with cisplatin at a dose of 20 mg/kg to induce acute liver damage. Barasertib was administered for five consecutive days at two different doses: 20 mg/kg and 40 mg/kg. **Results:** CIS administration markedly elevated serum LDH levels, hepatic MDA contents, and α -SMA expression compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$). BAS treatment significantly attenuated all these effects in a dose-dependent manner. BAS at 20 mg/kg reduced LDH activity, lipid peroxidation, and α -SMA immunoreactivity, while the 40 mg/kg dose produced superior protection. Histological analysis confirmed that BAS alleviated

hepatocyte damage and suppressed HSC activation, with minimal α -SMA immunoreactivity observed in the CIS+BAS40 group. **Conclusions:** BAS significantly alleviates CIS-induced hepatotoxicity through antioxidative, cytoprotective, and antifibrotic mechanisms, suggesting it as adjuvant therapy to reduce hepatotoxicity of cisplatin chemotherapy.

KEYWORDS: Aurora kinase; Barasertib; Cisplatin; Hepatotoxicity; Liver fibrosis; Drug repurposing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cisplatin (CIS) is a platinum-based chemotherapeutic agent used for treating solid malignancies like lung, ovary, and bladder, is known for its significant toxicities, including nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, ototoxicity, neurotoxicity, gastrointestinal toxicity, and retinal toxicity, which may limit its clinical use. (Mansour H. et al. 2024 ;Abd Rashid N et al. 2021; Tan WJT et al. 2023).

Cisplatin-induced hepatotoxicity is a disorder characterized by inflammation, mitochondrial dysfunction, hepatocyte degradation, and fibrosis, triggered by excessive reactive oxygen species generation (Dasari S et al. 2014; Katanić Stanković JS et al. 2023).

Aurora kinases, serine/threonine kinases, are crucial for cell cycle regulation, particularly during mitosis, Aurora kinase B is essential for chromosomal segregation, cytokinesis, and genomic integrity (Carmena M et al. 2009). Aurora kinase overexpression is linked to cancer, but it's also implicated in non-malignant pathological processes like inflammation and fibrosis (Ren X et al. 2023; Kasam RK et al. 2020).

Barasertib (BAS), a selective Aurora kinase B inhibitor, is being investigated as an anti-cancer medication due to its potential to disrupt cell cycle progression and induce cell death in rapidly proliferating tumor cells. It particularly inhibits Aurora B kinase, leading to mitotic arrest and cell death (Helfrich BA et al. 2016). BAS has shown promising preclinical and early clinical outcomes in cancer therapy, particularly in tumors with c-MYC amplification or overexpression, promoting mitotic arrest and apoptosis (Wilkinson RW et al. 2007; Tanaka K et al. 2021; Dennis M et al. 2012; Porcelli L et al. 2015). Preclinical studies show that inhibiting Aurora kinase B with BAS could attenuate fibroblast activation, and pulmonary fibrosis in experimental models by downregulating extracellular matrix gene expression and tissue remodeling (Kasam RK et al. 2020).

Involvement of Aurora kinases in cell death pathways and cytokine production suggests that aurora kinase inhibitors could be a promising therapeutic option for hepatoprotection in the context of CIS treatment.

Collectively, the aim of this study is to assess the potential preventive effect of BAS on CIS-induced hepatotoxicity in mice and investigate the underlying processes.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Drugs and chemicals

CIS was purchased as an injectable solution (50mg/50mL, CELON LABS, Telangana State, India). Barasertib was purchased as a pure powder from DC Chemicals (Shanghai, China).

2.2 Animals

Adult male BALB/c mice were obtained from VACSERA (Giza, Egypt) and housed in a controlled environment maintained at 25 °C under a 12 h/12 h light/dark cycle with free access to food and water.

2.3 Ethical approval

Experimental design was reviewed and accepted by the Mansoura University Animal Care and Use Committee (MU-ACUC), Egypt.

2.4 Experimental design

Mice were randomly divided into five groups (six mice each) as follows: **Group I (Control, CTRL)**; **Group II (BAS-40)** received daily i.p injections of BAS at dose of 40 mg/kg for 5 days (Kasam RK et al. 2020); **Group III (CIS)** received a single dose of CIS (20 mg/kg) (Sen S et al. 2013; Hashimoto T et al. 2022); **Group IV (CIS+BAS-20)** and **Group V (CIS+BAS-40)** were treated with BAS at dose of 20 mg/kg and 40 mg/kg, for 5 days respectively, along with a single dose of CIS on day two.

2.5 Sample collection and preparation

On day 6, blood samples were collected. The right median lobe of the liver was isolated and fixed in neutral buffered formalin (10% v/v) for immunohistochemical analyses of α -SMA. The left median lobe was isolated and homogenized in phosphate buffered saline for oxidative stress assessment.

2.6 Assessment of serum LDH

Serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH, Cat. No. LDH 25, Swemed diagnostics, Karnataka, India) was determined in the liver homogenate as per manufacturer`s instructions.

2.7 Assessment of redox status in the liver

The lipid peroxidation biomarker malondialdehyde (MDA, Cat. No. MD 2529, Bio-diagnostic, Giza, Egypt) was determined in the liver homogenate as per manufacturer`s instructions.

2.8 Immunohistochemistry

Immunohistochemical staining was conducted to assess the hepatic expression of alpha smooth muscle actin (α -SMA). After antigen retrieval, slides were incubated with antibodies against α -SMA (Cat No. GB111364, Servicebio, China). After rinsing with phosphate buffered saline, samples were incubated with secondary antibody (Cat. No. BAR1018, Biospes, China). The samples were then stained with diaminobenzidine. Then, slides were washed, dried, and photographed. Percentage of positively stained area per total area was assessed.

2.9 Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism V 8.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., CA, USA). Normally distributed data were analyzed using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey multiple comparisons post-hoc test and expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Impact of BAS20 and BAS40 on CIS-induced liver injury

Liver injury after the cisplatin challenge was evidenced by a significant elevation of LDH serum activities in comparison with the CTRL group (Fig. 1). However, administration of BAS (20 mg/kg) for 5 days with CIS significantly decreased level of LDH ($P < 0.001$) compared to CIS alone. Otherwise, a higher BAS dose (40 mg/kg) significantly decreased level of LDH ($P < 0.001$) compared to CIS alone. Notably, the effect of the higher dose was significantly higher than the lower one on serum LDH activities.

Figure 1: Impact of BAS20 and BAS40 on LDH that was increased by CIS injection.

Blood samples were collected at the end of the experiment to assess serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). Data are represented as mean \pm SD (n =6). * p<0.05, significantly different from CTRL, [§] p<0.05, significantly different from BAS40, [#] p<0.05, significantly different from CIS, & p<0.05, significantly different from CIS+BAS20, using One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey Kramer test.

3.2 Impact of BAS20 and BAS40 on CIS-induced oxidative stress in the liver

Cisplatin injection resulted in oxidative stress in the liver as indicated by a significant increase in the lipid peroxidation biomarker MDA compared to the CTRL group (Fig. 2). Meanwhile, BAS (20 and 40 mg/kg) significantly repressed hepatic MDA contents by compared to the CIS group. Notably, the effect of BAS (40 mg/kg) on MDA in the liver was significantly superior compared to the effect of BAS (20 mg/kg).

Figure 2: Impact of BAS40 and BAS20 on CIS-induced elevation of MDA.

Liver tissues were collected at the end of the experiment to assess MDA.

Data are represented as mean \pm SD (n =6). * p<0.05, significantly different from CTRL, [§] p<0.05, significantly different from BAS40, [#] p<0.05, significantly different from CIS, & p<0.05, significantly different from CIS+BAS20 using One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey Kramer test.

3.3 Impact of barasertib on CIS-induced elevation of α -SMA expression in the liver

The immunoexpression of α -SMA in the liver was addressed (Fig. 3). Our findings showed that the CIS group shows intense cytoplasmic α -SMA immunoreactivity in perivascular

hepatocytes while the control group has nearly negative immunoreactivity. CIS+BAS-20 group demonstrated moderate cytoplasmic α -SMA immunoreactivity in some perivascular hepatocytes where CIS+BAS-40 group had minimal cytoplasmic α -SMA immunoreactivity in a few perivascular hepatocytes. Additionally, the percentage of α -SMA positive area was assessed (Fig. 3). The CIS challenge significantly ($P < 0.001$) elevated hepatic α -SMA expression levels compared to the control group. Meanwhile, barasertib administration (20 mg/kg) with CIS significantly ($P < 0.001$) reduced the elevated α -SMA levels when compared to the CIS group, and these levels were further repressed by administration of barasertib at a dose of 40 mg/kg

Fig. 3: A) Representative micrographs of immuno-stained liver tissue sections demonstrating the effect of BAS-20 and BAS-40 on α -SMA expression in CIS-intoxicated mice (the upper panel: x10, bar= 100 μ m and the lower panel: x40, bar= 20 μ m). The control group shows normal hepatic architecture with no α -SMA immunoreactivity. The CIS group shows intense immunoreactivity in perivascular hepatocytes. The CIS+BAS-20 group shows moderate immunoreactivity in some perivascular hepatocytes. The CIS+BAS-40 group shows minimal immunoreactivity in

few perivascular hepatocytes. B) Percentages of α -SMA immunopositive areas. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. *, #, & significance difference compared to the control, CIS, and CIS+BAS-20 groups, respectively, using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey-Kramer multiple comparisons post hoc test.

4. DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates, for the first time, that BAS) an Aurora B kinase inhibitor, dose-dependently protected against CIS-induced hepatotoxicity. CIS administration resulted in marked hepatotoxicity, as evidenced by elevated serum LDH, enhanced oxidative stress (increased hepatic MDA), and exaggerated α -SMA expression reflecting hepatic stellate cell activation and early fibrogenic changes. Treatment with BAS (20 and 40 mg/kg) attenuated CIS-induced hepatotoxicity, with the higher dose exerting a more profound hepatoprotective impact.

Elevation of serum LDH following CIS exposure reflects hepatocellular damage and compromised membrane integrity, consistent with previous reports on CIS-induced systemic toxicity (Arany I et al. 2003; Yao X et al. 2007). BAS administration, specifically at 40 mg/kg, significantly reduced LDH levels, suggesting that the BAS preserves hepatocyte integrity and mitigates cellular leakage of cytosolic enzymes.

Oxidative stress is a well-established mechanism underlying CIS-induced organ injury. Cisplatin-induced oxidative stress is linked to its chemical structure, which causes redox imbalance and consequent cell injury by mediating the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Elmorsy EA et al. 2024; Yang, H. et al. 2018). Our finding established this by demonstrating a significant elevation of hepatic MDA, a marker of lipid peroxidation, after CIS administration. Notably, BAS treatment markedly reduced MDA content, highlighting a potent antioxidative impact of BAS. Aurora B kinase inhibition has been related to regulation of oxidative stress, that may illustrate the observed reduction of lipid peroxidation.

Another important finding in this study is the mitigation of CIS-induced α -SMA immunopositivity by BAS. Elevated α -SMA is an indicator of hepatic stellate cell activation, a crucial step in the initiation of hepatic fibrosis. Liver fibrosis is a condition where excess extracellular matrix proteins accumulate due to increased protein synthesis and impaired protein breakdown, affecting key markers like collagen and α -SMA (Khurana A et al. 2021).

CIS markedly elevated α -SMA expression in perivascular hepatocytes, suggesting fibrogenic responses secondary to hepatocellular injury and oxidative stress. BAS, particularly at 40 mg/kg, markedly attenuated α -SMA immunoreactivity, proposing its impact in restricting activation of HSC and preventing early fibrosis. This antifibrotic effect could be mediated via inhibition of oxidative stress. BAS has shown promise in reducing liver fibrosis by reducing collagen deposition, and attenuating Alpha-SMA expression (Dai G. et al. 2025; Tan Z et al. 2021).

Collectively, our findings suggest that BAS exerts hepatoprotective effects against CIS-induced hepatotoxicity by (i) preserving hepatocyte integrity, (ii) attenuating oxidative stress, and (iii) inhibiting fibrogenesis. These results align with emerging evidence that Aurora kinase inhibitors might modulate not only cell cycle regulation in cancer therapy but also cellular stress responses and tissue injury.

In conclusion, BAS significantly alleviates CIS-induced hepatotoxicity through antioxidative, cytoprotective, and antifibrotic mechanisms, suggesting it as adjuvant therapy to reduce hepatotoxicity of cisplatin chemotherapy.

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Author Contributions

Faisal Alqussair: Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, writing original draft. **Mahmoud Elshal:** Methodology Writing–review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation. **Mirhan N. Makled:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation. **Nashwa Abu-Elsaad:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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